

BIODIVERSITY ANALYSIS PIPELINE

About this document

This document constitutes ACROPICS protocol in Biodiversity and Ecosystem services assessment, ie. the Biodiversity Analysis Pipeline, deliverable 1 of ACROPICS Work Package 3 (D.3.1.). This document was produced by Alexandra Auguste, INRAE, and Elodie Vercken, INRAE, based in Institut Sophia Agrobiotech (ISA), mixed research center of INRAE, University Côte d’Azur and CNRS.

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1. Introduction

This document constitutes the deliverable D.3.1.- Biodiversity Analysis Pipeline, of ACROPICS Work Package 3 which aims to set up the data collection protocol of the biodiversity assessment to be conducted and benchmarked in the ACROPICS project. The biodiversity assessment protocol (D.3.1.) will serve as the foundation for the data collection for the deliverable D.3.3. Biodiversity Analysis data, with a submission deadline on the 31st of December 2026.

1.1. Objective and expected results of the biodiversity assessment protocol

The overall objective of the biodiversity assessment protocol is to complement and develop the data collected via the TAPE tool evaluation (Tool for Agroecological Performance Evaluation), via WP4, conducted in each Sustainable Agroecological System (SAS) included in the ACROPICS project. While the TAPE tool evaluation offers an excellent opportunity to explore relationships between ecological transition, biodiversity, and ecosystem service indices, the ACROPICS project aim to take the biodiversity element of this tool, one step further by the addition of a supplementary biodiversity assessment. This supplementary biodiversity assessment permit for each SAS to get a deeper comprehension of the impact of their agroecological innovations and practices of the biodiversity in their respective system.

This supplementary biodiversity assessment holds a value both for the understanding of the agroecological transitions within each of the SAS in addition to bringing a methodological reflection and development to the TAPE tool, developed under the lead of the FAO.

As stated in the DoA of the ACROPICS grant agreement (task 3.2. in WP3), the activities in this deliverable aims to impulse a collective effort of the SAS and support organisations (INRAE, RUG, INTA, CUYO, UCM, UHF) on biodiversity analyses. The expected results from the roll out of the biodiversity assessment protocol is to obtain a data set of 10 samples from approximately 6 of the SAS. The collected data, analysis and results will be extensively used in WP6 for large-scale diffusion highlighting the relationship between agroecological transition and biodiversity in the agroecological systems included in the ACROPICS project.

1.2. Online training of the biodiversity assessment protocol

Online training program

To collect a maximum amount of biodiversity assessment data, a set of online trainings were organised for the SAS included in the ACROPICS project. The online training plan was constructed as following:

Part 1:

Two online training sessions of 1h30 each, were proposed on the 9th and 13th of february 2026. The trainings included a presentation of the Biodiversity Assessment protocols followed by a Q&A and common discussion between researchers and SAS representatives. Two sessions were proposed to the SAS in addition to being recorded and uploaded on the ACROPICS intranet for those wishing to watch the trainings in replay. The two online trainings had approximately 50 participants in total, including representatives from both the SAS and other member organisations of the ACROPICS project.

Part 2:

Following the online training, the proposed plan includes a data collection phase of biodiversity samples from the SAS (predominantly those situated in the northern hemisphere) during the spring and summer of 2026. The objective includes the collection of a set of 10 samples from each SAS via the application of the biodiversity assessment protocols. While the major part of the biodiversity assessment data collection will be implemented during the spring of 2026, a complementary data collection phase may be conducted during the autumn of 2026 (depending on the location of the SAS and their respective flowering season).

Part 3:

A final session of online training will be proposed after the biodiversity assessment data collection in order to follow up on the data collection process, address encountered difficulties and answer questions which might have emerged in the SAS.

Practical and logistical needs in SAS to conduct the protocols

Following the first part of the online training program, a survey (see annex) was sent out to the participants (SAS representatives), inquiring about their practical and logistical needs in order to conduct the data collection using the biodiversity assessment protocol. In order to maximise the data collection samples, the biodiversity Assessment protocol was designed to be simple, and adapted to be carried out by non-experts relying on locally available human resources in the SAS (interns, students, laboratory technicians). If this proves difficult for the SAS, the survey also opened up for SAS to express their needs for additional assistance for the implementation of the protocols, ex. Secondments, financial support, materiel etc. To each participant wishing to engage in the biodiversity assessment data collection, sampling kits (including traps and recording devices), along with a practical guide detailing the sampling protocols step by step, will be sent out by ACROPICS coordinator INRAE.

2. Biodiversity Assessment Protocol

2.1. General information

Why sampling ?

- ✓ Investigate the relationship between the tape score and the abundance or diversity of living organisms, particularly arthropods (insects, spiders, millipedes, etc.), birds and bats.
- ✓ Assess the predictive power of the tape score on i) neutral biodiversity and ii) the effectiveness of certain ecosystem services.

Where sampling ?

- ✓ At 10 sites per SAS, spaced at least 2 km apart, where the tape score has been or will be assessed.
- ✓ Except for audio recordings, you will be asked for applying protocols twice: once at the center of the site and once at the edge outside the site.

Red crosses represent traps (e.g. pitfall). White square represents the area where crop is cultivated. Edges are places immediately adjacent to the site but not cultivated.

When sampling ?

During the flowering peak period of the main crop or of the region if the crop produces few or no flowers.

- ✓ Only in good weather.

How sampling ?

- ✓ These protocols do not require any special knowledge. They have been designed to be applicable by non-specialists.
- ✓ A kit containing all the necessary equipment will be provided by INRAE (except for the 4 empty water bottles that will contain the salt water and a sheet of paper).

- ✓ In Appendix, you will find a list and photos of the equipment sent. Each item in the kit is identified with its own number. In each protocol, the items will be named and identified with their number so that they can be easily recognized (e.g., Pitfall trap (No.), bulb planter (No.)).
- ✓ Please read the documents in advance, as there are a few small things to do the day before or a few days before going into the field.
- ✓ The protocols are independent of each other and can be applied in any order. However, to ensure that nothing is overlooked, we recommend that you follow the order suggested in this document.

How long is sampling ?

- ✓ The total sampling and assessment time was estimated at around five days if the samples were sent back to INRAE for identification (four days in the field and one day in the laboratory).
- ✓ Here is an estimate of how long each protocol will take in the field and at each site:

Protocol	D Day (Time in min/site)	The day after (Time in min/site)
Pitfall traps	20	15
Pan traps	25	25
Audio recordings	10	10
Tea bags	15	15
pH and water retention	10	10
Total	80	75

Tip: for practical reasons, the protocols are described separately. However, it may be more convenient and quicker to apply all the protocols to the center of the plot first, then start again at the edge of the plot. This avoids having to go back and forth between the center and the edge.

2.2. Sampling soil fauna with pitfall traps

Objective/principle

Pitfall traps are a passive sampling method used to evaluate the abundance and diversity of soil macrofauna, such as ground beetles and earwigs (Figure 1). They are containers buried in the ground that contain a killing solution. Small animals that fall into the trap are unable to escape.

Figure 1-Pitfall trap

Stepwise method description

The day before sampling (10 minutes):

- Step 1: **Warning! you need to provide 4 empty bottles of water of 1L and one sheet of paper.** Prepare the killing solution (brine water) by adding the entire contents of a tube of salt (No.1) using a paper sheet funnel in a 1-liter bottle provided by you (Figure 2). The salt will not dissolve completely, resulting in a very salty liquid that will kill and preserve the insects during the 24-hour sampling period. This brine will be also used for pan traps.
- Step 2: Put the freezer packs (No.2) in the freezer.

Figure 2

D Day Sampling (20 minutes):

Warning! Four pitfall traps will be placed per site: two in the center and two on the edge.

Step 3: Once you are on the plot, choose a first location in the center.

Step 4: Using the bulb planter (No.3), dig one hole 10 cm deep (Figure 3). If the soil is too dry, water it beforehand.

Step 5: Place the pot in the hole after removing its lid. Pour salt water into the pot until it is half full (Figure 4), then add a few drops of washing-up liquid using the pipette (Figure 5).

Figure 3, 4, 5.

Step 6: Fill around the pot with soil, making sure the edges are level with or slightly below the ground. This is important because walking insects will not fall into the trap if the pot's edges are above ground level, even slightly (Figure 6, 7).

Figure 6,7.

Step 7: Cover the pot with the plastic plate so that, in the event of light rain, water does not fill the trap (Figure 8). Plant a stick near the trap and attach a piece of barrier tape to it to serve as a visual marker when you come to collect the traps (Figure 9).

Figure 8,9.

Step 8: Dig another hole about 3 meters from the first one and repeat step 5 to 7.

Step 9: Fill in the provided field data sheet (See Field Data Sheet 1), noting the kind of trap (Pitfall/Pan trap), the installation date and time, the SAS code, the plot code, the GPS coordinates recorded on your mobile phone (latitude and longitude) and the location of the trap in the site (Center or Edge).

Step 10: Choose a location at the edge of the plot and repeat steps 4 to 9 for the two last traps.

Step 11: Leave the pots in place for 24 hours.

The day after sampling (25 min) :

Step 12: Go back to the center of the plot where you put the first two pots. Prepare a sieve placing a piece of stockings upon the plastic pot (Figure 10).

Figure 10

Step 13: Remove the plastic plate above each hole. Remove the first pot and pour its contents onto the sieve. The insects will be retained by the sieve. Repeat with the second pot in the center of the plot, using the same sieve.

Step 14: Remove the siever containing the insects, fold it, and place it in the sample bag (N°). Fill the bag with 96° ethanol using the pipette N° and add a label (Labels sheet) to which you will have written the following information in pencil beforehand (**warning! Do not use a pen to write on the label as the ink will be erased by the alcohol**): SAS code, plot code, date, hour, location (center or edge) and kind of trap (eg Pitfall here). Close the sample bag by folding it over itself (Figure 11,12,13).

Figure 11,12, 13

Step 15: Place the sample bag in a zip-lock plastic bag (1 zip-lock bag per site used for pitfall and pan traps).

Step 16: Repeat steps 12 to 14 for the two last traps at the edge of the site.

Step 17: Place the zip-lock plastic bag containing all the sample bags in the freezer bag with the freezer pack.

Step 18: Once back at the laboratory, store the samples in the freezer at -20°C until they can be identified, either locally or by shipping them to INRAE. If identification of the organisms sampled is to be carried out locally, the necessary identification tools will be provided. Only identification at the morphotype level will be required.

2.3. Sampling pollinators with pan traps

Objective/principle

Pan traps are a passive sampling method used to evaluate abundance and diversity of pollinators (bees, syrphs, wasps, ...). There are 3 bowls painted with white, blue or yellow fluorescent paint and, filled with a killing, preservative solution (Figure 14).

Figure 14

Stepwise method description

Warning! Two set of 3 pan traps will be placed per site: one in the center and one on the edge.

D day sampling (25 minutes):

Step 1: Once you are on the plot, choose a first location in the center.

Step 2: Set up the first pan traps. Drive the PVC tube (No.) 10 cm into the ground using the mallet (No. 11) and ensure it is stable. The top of the tube should be either above the surrounding plants or at the same level, but not below them (Figure 14).

Step 3: Hang one pot of each color (N°) (one blue, one yellow and one white) by inserting the steel wire into the holes in the PVC tube provided for this purpose.

Step 4: Fill each pot with brine until it is just under half full, then add a pipette of washing-up liquid.

Step 5: Fill in the provided field data sheet (Field Data Sheet 1), noting the kind of trap (Pitfall/Pan/Audio trap), the installation date and time, the SAS code, the plot code, the GPS coordinates recorded on your mobile phone (latitude and longitude) and the location of the trap in the site (Center or Edge).

Step 6: Choose a location at the edge of the plot and repeat steps 2 to 5.

Step 7: Leave the traps in place for 24 hours.

The day after sampling (25 min):

Step 8: Go back to the center of the plot where you put the first set of pan traps.

Step 9: Prepare a sieve placing a piece of stockings (N°) upon the plastic pot (N°) (Figure 15).

Figure 15

Step 10: Remove the yellow trap and pour its contents onto the sieve. The insects will be retained by the sieve. **Warning! Do not mix the contents of the three traps (1 sample bag per trap).**

Step 11: Remove the siever containing the insects, fold it, and place it in the sample bag (N°). Fill the bag with 96° ethanol using the pipette N° and add a label (Labels sheet) to which you will have written the following information in pencil beforehand (**warning! Do not use a pen to write on the label as the ink will be erased by the alcohol**): SAS code, plot code, date, hour, location (center or edge), kind of trap and its color (e.g. Pan trap/yellow here). Close the sample bag by folding it over itself (Figure 16,17,18).

Figure 16,17, 18

Step 12: Place the sample bag in the zip-lock plastic bag already containing the pitfall traps samples of the site.

Step 13: Repeat steps 9 to 12 for the blue trap at the center of the site.

Step 14: Repeat steps 9 to 12 for the white trap at the center of the site.

Step 15: Go back to the edge of the plot where you put the second set of pan traps. Repeat steps 9 to 14 for the traps at the edge of the site.

Step 16: Place the zip-lock plastic bag containing all the sample bags of the site in the freezer bag with the freezer pack.

Step 17: Once back at the laboratory, store the samples in the freezer at -20°C until they can be identified, either locally or by shipping them to INRAE. If identification of the organisms sampled is to be carried out locally, the necessary identification tools will be provided. Only identification at the morphotype level will be required.

2.4. Sampling aerie fauna with audio recordings

Objective/principle

This method involves recording birds, insects and bats at both sunset and sunrise using audio recorders called Audiomoth (Figure 19). Once identified, the number of species will be counted.

Stepwise method description

Figure 19

Warning! Do not take out the Audiomoth from its waterproof. If the batteries are removed the configuration will be lost.

D day sampling (10 mn) :

Warning! Two audio recorders are provided. The Audiomoth with the red dot on the bottom right is configured to record birdsong. The other recorder, which has a yellow sticker, is configured to record bats and orthoptera. The protocol is identical for both recorders.

Step 1: Choose an attachment point (preferably a tree; but if that is not possible, use a pole, a fence picket, ...) at the edge of the plot.

Step 2: Open the waterproof case (No.). Without taking out the Audiomoth, push the switch to the left and set it to Custom. Close the waterproof case (Figure 20, 21 ,22).

Figure 21- Position of the switch.

Step 3: Hang the Audiomoth at approximately 1.5 meters (Figure 22). If there are no accessible branches, tape the bag around the trunk. Point the microphone (circled in red in Figure 23) hole towards an open area, as branches can cause echoes that make identification more difficult. Recordings will start automatically at the set times.

Figure 23

Step 4: Attach a piece of barrier tape to a branch of the tree, not too close, to serve as a visual marker when you come to collect the Audiomoth.

Step 5: Fill in the provided field data sheet (Field Data Sheet 1), noting the kind of trap (Pitfall/Pan/Audio), the installation date and time, the SAS code, the plot code, the GPS coordinates recorded on your mobile phone (latitude and longitude).

Step 6: If possible, choose another attachment point, at least 50 meters from the first one and repeat step 2 to 5.

Step 7: Leave the Audiomoth in place for 24 hours.

The day after sampling (10 min):

Step 8: Go back to the tree plot where you put the first Audiomoth.

Step 9: Remove the waterproof case containing the Audiomoth from the branch/trunk. Open the waterproof case and, without taking out the Audiomoth, set the switch of the Audiomoth back to USB/OFF. Close the waterproof case.

Step 10: Keep both audiomoths in the bubble wrap envelope (No.) until shipment.

2.5. Measuring degradation of organic matter with tea bags

Objective/principle

This method provides an easy way to evaluate the degradation of organic matter by soil organisms using tea bags. It simply involves burying tea bags in the ground. Weighing them before and after burial allows to estimate how much matter has been lost over three months (Figure 24).

Figure 24

Stepwise method description

Warning! Eight tea bags will be buried per site: 4 in the center and 4 on the edge.

D day (15 minutes):

Step 1: Once you are on the plot, choose a first location in the center. Take one Lipton Green tea bags (N°) and one Rooibos tea bag (N°).

Step 2: Fill in the provided field data sheet (Field Data Sheet 2), noting the bag code, the installation date, the SAS code, the plot code, the GPS coordinates recorded on your mobile phone (latitude and longitude) and the location of the trap in the site (Center or Edge).

Step 3: Bury on the both teabags in separate, about 8 cm-deep holes, ca 15 cm apart using the auger (N°). Keep the labels visible above the soil. Mark the burial site with a stick

(N°) and attach a piece of barrier tape to it to serve as a visual marker when you come to collect the tea bags (Figure 25).

Step 4: Repeat step 1 to 3 for the second set of tea bags.

Figure 25

Step 5: Choose a location at the edge of the plot and repeat steps 1 to 4.

After about 3 months (15 minutes):

Step 6: Go back to the center of the plot where you put the first two sets of tea bags. Recover the tea bags.

Step 7: Introduce each tea bag in a sample bag (1 tea bag per sample bag). Add silica gel. Introduce the sample bags in a zip-lock plastic bag (1 zip-lock plastic bag per SAS).

Step 8: Repeat steps 6 to 7 for the tea bags at the edge of the site.

Warning Send us the tea bags as soon as possible.

2.6. Measuring soil pH

Objective/principle

pH value influences the activity and the composition of microbial communities. Measuring pH involves dissolving a soil sample in demineralised water and then dipping a pH paper strip into it. The colour of the pH paper then reflects the pH.

Stepwise method description

Warning! Two soil samples will be collect per site: one in the center and one on the edge.

D day sampling (10 minutes):

Step 1: Once you are on the plot, choose a first location in the center.

Step 2: Remove litter and collect soil sample using the planting trowel (10 cm deep), and put soil sample in a zip-lock plastic bag (Figure 26). Add a label to which you will have written the following information in pencil beforehand (**warning! Do not use a pen to write on the label as the ink will be erased by the alcohol**): SAS code, plot code, date, location (center or edge).

Figure 26

Step 3: Repeat step 2 at the edge of the site.

Laboratory procedure (120 minutes) :

Step 4: To measure pH. At the laboratory, put a glass (N°) on the weighing scale and tare it. Add about 20 g of soil sample in the plastic glass. Note the SAS and plot codes on the glass with the marker. Repeat this step for all the soil sample of the day.

Step 5: Measure 25 ml in the plastic test tube and add it in the first glass and homogenize the solution without shaking too vigorously. Repeat this step for all the soil sample of the day.

Step 6: Let stand for about 1 hour.

Step 7: Moisten a pH paper strip for a few seconds. Compare the color with the color chart. Repeat the process for all other samples, using a new pH paper strip each time.

2.7. Equipment

Trap	N°	Name	Number	Picture
Pitfall trap	1	Salt tube	10	
	2	Freezer pack	1	
	3	Bulb planter	1	

3. Conclusion

This document presented the ACROPICS project's biodiversity assessment protocol (D.3.1.) which will be implemented in the project's SAS during the year of 2026 (predominantly spring and summer). Several online training sessions, presenting the protocol were conducted in February 2026. The data collection, conducted in the ACROPICS SAS using the biodiversity assessment protocol, will be used to produce the data necessary for the WP3 deliverable D.3.3. Biodiversity Analysis Data, submission deadline in the 31st December 2026.

4. Annex

4.1. Online survey

Biodiversity and ecosystem services assessment

Dear participant of the Biodiversity Assessment training,

This short survey aims to obtain your feedback on the sampling protocols presented during the training. Through this survey, we would also like to know whether you'd like to participate in the biodiversity assessment data collection, conducted in the context of the ACROPICIS project. If so, please fill in your needs in the last section of the survey.

Thank you !

There are 14 questions in this survey.

*Full name:

*Institution / Organization:

*Your role / position within the organization:

*Are you part of a SAS within the ACROPICIS project? if yes, which one ?

Choose one of the following answers

Yes

No

Please enter your comment here:

How familiar are you with the proposed sampling protocols?

Choose one of the following answers

Very familiar

Somewhat familiar

Slightly familiar

Not familiar yet

Other:

Overall, how would you rate the clarity of the sampling protocols?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

- Very clear
- Clear
- Neither clear nor unclear
- Unclear
- Very unclear

How feasible do you consider the implementation of the first protocol (pitfall traps to sample soil fauna)?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

- Very easy to implement
- Easy to implement
- Moderately difficult
- Difficult
- Very difficult

How feasible do you consider the implementation of the second protocol (pan traps to sample pollinators)?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

- Very easy to implement
- Easy to implement
- Moderately difficult
- Difficult
- Very difficult

How feasible do you consider the implementation of the third protocol (Audio recordings) ?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

- Very easy to implement
- Easy to implement
- Moderately difficult
- Difficult
- Very difficult

How feasible do you consider the implementation of the fourth protocol (Tea bags method)?

● Choose one of the following answers

- Very easy to implement
- Easy to implement
- Moderately difficult
- Difficult
- Very difficult

How feasible do you consider the implementation of the fifth protocol (pH measure) ?

● Choose one of the following answers

- Very easy to implement
- Easy to implement
- Moderately difficult
- Difficult
- Very difficult

What challenges or limitations do you anticipate in implementing these protocols?

*Are you willing to participate in the biodiversity assessment ? Please specify why/why not in the box to the right.

● Choose one of the following answers

- Willing to participate
- No willing to participate

Please enter your comment here:

Please specify any conditions, support needs, or suggestions that could facilitate your participation in the sampling campaign.